

Workshop: Research Data Lifecycle and Machine-actionable Data Management Plans

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Abstract

This report describes outputs the workshop on *Research Data Lifecycle and Machine-actionable Data Management Plans* organised in Vienna on 22 November 2017. The workshop was organized by the RDA DMP Common Standards WG in order to collect requirements of various stakeholders involved in research data management for machine-actionable data management plans.

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Introduction and objectives

The current manifestation of a DMP—a static document often created before a project begins—only contributes to the perception that DMPs are an annoying administrative exercise. What they really are—or at least should be—is an integral part of research practice, since today most research across all disciplines involves data, code, and other digital components.

We still need a human-readable narrative, but there is now widespread recognition that, underneath, the DMP could have more thematic, machine-actionable richness with added value for all stakeholders: researchers, funders, repository managers, ICT providers, librarians, etc.

The Research Data Alliance working group on DMP Common Standards works to implement machine-actionable DMPs. The larger goal is to improve the experience for all involved by exchanging information across research tools and systems and embedding DMPs in existing workflows. As a result, parts of the DMPs can be automatically generated and shared with other collaborators or funders. To achieve this goal we need:

1. a well-defined research data lifecycle,
2. a research data management infrastructure,
3. a common data model for machine-actionable DMPs.

In this workshop we will focus on the research data lifecycle and will seek to identify who the stakeholders at each stage of the research lifecycle are. We will discuss which information they provide and which information they need and how existing and future systems and services can support and potentially automate this information flow.

The results of the workshop will contribute to the open consultation of the RDA DMP Common Standards working group. The workshop is a satellite event of the RDA Europe meeting that takes place on the 23rd of November. For this reason we are expecting a good balance of Austrian and international participants who represent different stakeholders, such as, funders, repository managers, research administrators, ICT operators, data librarians, and researchers.

The workshop will be run in an interactive mode, with minimal amount of presentations and with focus on free exchange of ideas during moderated sessions. The participation is free of charge.

Agenda

The workshop took place on 22 November 2017, 14:00 - 17:00 at the Universitätsbibliothek Wien, Universität Wien, Universitätsring 1, 1010Wien, Hauptbibliothek in the „Kleiner Kursraum“.

The agenda was:

- you learn about us
- we learn about you
- setting the scene for exercise 1
- exercise 1 - stakeholders needs within research data lifecycle
- coffee break
- setting the scene for exercise 2
- exercise 2 - flow of information between stakeholders

- Wrap-up

Slides used during the workshop can be found: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1066109>

Participants

There were 15 participants representing various Austrian institutions and having different roles with respect to data management. Table 1 summarises organizations and roles of participants.

Table 1 Profile of participants.

Organization	Role
Universität Wien	Repository Manager
Technische Universität Wien	Data processing specialist
The Austrian Social Science Data Archive	Research Data Manager
Zentraler Informatiker Dienst (ZID)	Research support
FWF - Der Wissenschaftsfonds	Data Processing Specialist
Wirtschaftsuniversität Wien	Open Access Manager
Medizinische Universität Wien	Research Administrator
University of Innsbruck	Research Service
	IT services
	Cataloguer

Figure 1 Workshop participants working on the first exercise.

Exercise 1

Description

There were two groups. Each group worked to define user stories that express needs of various stakeholders involved in the research data lifecycle. For more information see workshop slides <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1066109> and the open GitHub consultation: <https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/user-stories>

Results

This section presents the user stories created by each group.

Group A

#planning

As a researcher, I want to know about costs, to plan my research.

As a researcher, I want to know topics mandatory and similar in all DMPs, so that I can quickly write it and save time.

As a researcher, I want to know whom to contact, to write my DMP.

As a researcher, I want to know where to store my data, so that it remains saved and accessible.

As a legal officer, I want to know about data sensitivity, to establish sharing options.

As a repository operator, I want to know the kind of data to evaluate the storage size and system.

#project

As an ethics manager, I want to be informed about the data, to check for sensitivity of data.

As a metadata manager, I need a short description of project, to be informed for the metadata description.

As a repository manager, I want metadata in additional languages, to allow for multilingual data archive.

As a repository manager, I want the researcher to know about documentation and metadata standards, to make archiving easier.

As a repository manager, I need details on the type of data, to check if the archiving can be arranged.

#publication

As a researcher I want to know how long it will take to archive, to plan further steps.

As a researcher I need to know about licenses, to figure out how to share.

As a repository manager, I need to know about anonymization status of data.

Group B

#planning

As a project funder, I need to know how many resources are need during the project to calculate costs.

As a research support officer, I want to know what kind of support the PI/project lead is looking for/needs, so we can allocate manpower accordingly.

As a rector, I need to know how many projects are proposed/admitted.

As a project lead I need to know whom to ask what resources exist at my institution to be able to fill the DMP.

As a rector I need to implement central points of information on RDM to make sure scientists know whom to ask.

As an institute, I want to know how many people will be employed to set up their workspaces in time.

As a rector, I need to know how many data will be stored to plan long term resources.

As a funder, I want to get a plan from the PIs about data management.

#project

As a PI, I want to know who owns the data to know what I am allowed to do with it.

As a PI, I want to plan what kind of data I want to record/store to ensure it will possible to store it.

As a PI, I want to know how secure data is to ensure legal compliance.

As an IT officer, I want to know how secure data is to ensure legal compliance.

As a funder, I want to know how secure data is to ensure legal compliance.

As a research support officer, I want to ensure compliance to the funders' rules to ensure all costs will be accepted.

As a PI, I want to properly record all metadata so I can ensure proper running of the project in case of staff changes.

As a PI, I want to know whether I am allowed to generate data (ethical stewardship) to know whether I can even deliver the project outcomes.

As a PI, I want to know what kind of metadata I need so I can record this in time.

#publication

As research evaluation manager I want to ensure all data are quoted correctly with our affiliation so they are counted towards our citation counts.

Exercise 2

Description

This exercise focused on understanding flow of information between the stakeholders involved in the research data management. Each of the groups filled out a table. The themes are based on the DCC themes: <https://github.com/DMPRoadmap/roadmap/wiki/Themes>. Each group decided on its own which themes to discuss.

Results

Group A

Theme ¹	Provided		Needed	
	BY	WHEN	BY	WHEN
IPR	Researcher	Planning	Legal Advisor	Post production
			Repository	Publication
			Project Consortium	Planning
Storage	Data Provider	Planning	Repository	Post production
Metadata	Repository	Production	Researcher	Publication
Data	Researcher	Publication & Planning	Repository	Publication

¹ <https://github.com/DMPRoadmap/roadmap/wiki/Themes>

Sharing			Funder	Planning
Budget Calculation	Researcher	Planning	Repository Funder	Planning
Data Collection	Researcher	Planning	Ethics committee Funder	Planning

Group B

Theme	Provided		Needed	
	BY	WHEN	BY	WHEN
IPR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal department • Funder 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principal Investigator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning throughout lifecycle
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rectorate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repository Operator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At publication
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At point of use
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data creator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At point of data creation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher/creator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At point of re-use/publication • To provide/deposit to repository
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other end-users & collaborators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Point of re-use
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publisher • Repository operator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When publishing • At ingest
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portfolio manager • Quality manager 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End of project? -> statistical purpose

Storage & Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researcher/data creator • IT department 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning phase • Throughout lifecycle 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers • Funders (compliance) • Compliance/legal officer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning /data production
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT department 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning
Data volume	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data creator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning • Creation phase update 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IT department • Repository operator • Funding body • Resource maanger 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • planning
Preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data creator • Funding body • Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation (university) • Repository operator 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning (commitments)